

Resilient Monitoring of the Structural Performance of Reinforced Concrete Bridges using Guided Waves

D V Achillopoulou & S A Mitoulis

Civil and Environmental Engineering Department, University of Surrey, Guildford, United Kingdom

N K Stamataki

Civil Engineering Department, Democritus University of Thrace, Xanthi, Greece

ABSTRACT: Structural Health Monitoring of the deflections of a reinforced concrete bridge deck strengthened with Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) or composite materials can help towards obtaining predictions of failures. Data regarding span deflection, FRP debondings or failures and concrete crack patterns, acquired by guided waves on interfaces of concrete substrate and FRP measures are used in order to represent the damage propagation of the strengthened bridge deck over time. The failure indexes of the interfaces help towards a strategy for maintenance and asset management based on potential risk that derives from structural data. This resilient strategic monitoring of interfaces is a practical, expedient, long-distant tool to estimate the efficiency of the interfaces (Interface Efficiency Indices-InterFeis) and the risk level of the asset with no disruption of traffic or in nonapproachable areas. The monitoring of the time history of data concerning the structural integrity, assesses the structural performance of the bridge against critical loads, combined phenomena, extreme events, climate change or other uncertainties of design or of its life-cycle and can be integrated in bridge design guidelines towards infrastructural safety and resilience of the transportation network, saving valuable time and resources.

1 INTRODUCTION

Transport assets and in particular bridges present the continuous need to extend their lifecycle. During their life the structural members are exposed to various conditions increased traffic loads, natural, environmental and human induced hazards, extreme events, overloading and various unpredicted environmental conditions due to climate change. As such, the structural integrity is affected and the capacity is questionable. Especially for bridges designed with past codes and standards, or even the ones that have already reached or approaching the end of their lifetime, retrofitting measures are often applied. Over the past decades the use of composites, e.g. fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) strengthening schemes are becoming more and more popular especially due to the high strength they offer to the final cross section and because of their minute dimensions that do not practically change the initial dimensions of the structural members. There are various techniques (sheets, laminates, near-surface-mounted, externally pre-stressed etc.) either for flexural retrofitting or for shear enhancement of the structural components.

In order to design and apply any strengthening schemes, the assessment of the asset is essential. Due to the uncertainties in the data considered for the assessment and the accuracy needed for a safe evaluation of the situation in which the asset is, monitoring can be the solution for eliminating uncertainties. Monitoring of the condition and especially Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) helps toward the better understanding of the performance as well as defining/detecting any failures, damages etc. Even though

there are numerous techniques, types of sensors and metrics, as well as numerous interpretation methods, still monitoring data can be either helpful or confusing.

Nowadays, especially after strengthening mitigation measures are applied in an asset, there is a lack of data regarding monitoring of the enhanced performance. The key element of the strengthened structural elements is the interface and its capacity to transfer loads (Achillopoulou et al. 2017, Sayed-Ahmed et al. 2009). The quantification of the efficiency of the interface of concrete substrate and FRP integrated measure is still under research. For the first time in literature, the interface is the main subject of monitoring. The proposed Interface Efficiency Indices represent different kind of damages (concrete substrate or FRP delamination/ crushing) derived by the deflections of both materials and can be a reliable tool toward defining the resilience of both structural members and the asset.

The paper is divided in 5 sections. Section 2 describes how monitoring can be proven beneficial for quantifying resilience of an asset with reliability. Section 3 describes the interface efficiency indices that are derived as a tool to evaluate whether there is a disruption in the stress flow and the capacity of the interface to transfer loads due to damages. Section 4 presents the finite element model which is developed to simulate two cases of a damaged bridge beam with external flexural FRP laminate strengthening: a) for extensive damaged concrete substrate and b) for FRP decreased cross section (due to e.g. failure, debonding, delamination). Finally, Section 5 summarizes the work and the conclusions of the research.

2 MONITORING-BASED RESILIENCE

2.1 Resilience of monitored assets

There is a wide range of monitoring techniques (Iyer et al. 2005, Katunin et al. 2015, Kundu 2014) and monitored measurands (see Section 3) that can help engineers improve their knowledge and assess with higher reliability level. The asset's (e.g. bridge, tunnel, embankment) resilience can be expressed as a function of the capacity of its components, especially the structural members (e.g. beams, beams, plates, columns, piers). The capacity differs from the structural member to the asset, but also is influenced by the nature of the stressors (Dong et al. 2013, Fragngopol 2011). For example, the degradation of capacity follows a different rate when the stressor causes a cumulative damage (Figure 1I) such as corrosion, while when the stressor has a blast influence (Figure 1II) the degradation of capacity is simultaneous, especially when natural hazards or catastrophic events take place, or the stress state causes extended failures such as debondings, failures on the substrate or delamination and failures of the elastic material (FRP). Figure 1 shows the different distinct periods at the life-cycle of a structural component and the asset. These periods can be different if monitoring of critical measurands is done.

Monitoring influences in different ways: a) compresses the post-damage response time, b) helps recover to the initial structural state faster, c) increases the reliability level of data and d) prevents from starting adaptation from a low residual capacity ratio. The uncertainties that follow each period are higher in the case that no monitoring is done. In fact, in this case, there are periods of limited knowledge regarding the structural integrity of the members. The uncertainties are also increased regarding the estimation of the loss of capacity. On the contrary, monitoring gives early warnings resulting to less extensive mitigation measures especially at an earlier time, without necessarily having degraded lower than the threshold of the critical level.

Table 1 includes the legend of Figure 1 and explains in detail the different curves, the characteristic values of the time axis and the capacity level.

Table1: Legend of Figure 1

1	—	No monitoring- recovery <100%	t_0	Starting function time of the asset
2	—	Continuous monitoring from the beginning	t_{dam}^I	Time of the initiation of important accumulation of damage
3	- - -	Monitoring during recovery period	t_{str}^{pla}	Time of the initiation of strategic plan for mitigation
4	—	No monitoring- recovery 100%	t_{res}^{mit}	Time of response for mitigation measures- no monitoring
5	- - -	Adaptation with monitoring	t_{rec}^M	Time of recovery of capacity after applying mitigation measures- no monitoring
6	- - -	Adaptation with monitoring after 100% recovery	t_{end}^I	Initial end of life-cycle according to design
7	- - -	Extension of life-cycle		
		c_{rec}		Capacity level after mitigation measures without monitoring
		c_{cr}^M		Critical capacity to design and apply mitigation measures with monitoring
		$c_{critical}$		Critical capacity to design and apply mitigation measures without monitoring
		$c_{residual}$		Residual capacity prior to design and apply mitigation measures without monitoring
		$c_{residual}^M$		Residual capacity prior to design and apply mitigation measures with monitoring
		t_{rest}^M		Time of response for mitigation measures with monitoring- EARLY WARNING TIME
		t_{rec}^M		Time of recovery of capacity after applying mitigation measures with monitoring
		t_{ada}^M		Time of adaptation of capacity after applying mitigation measures with monitoring
		t_{ada}		Time of adaptation of capacity after applying mitigation measures without monitoring
		t_{end}^{ext}		End time of life-cycle after adaptation

Cumulative: e.g. aging, corrosion, fatigue, scour, slopes, ground movements and settlements, deflections, traffic demands

Natural hazards: e.g. seismic event, flush floods, landslide, fire

Figure 1: Monitoring-based resilience throughout the life-cycle of an asset due to: I) cumulative damages, II) natural hazards

2.2 Monitoring of a strengthened bridge deck

Figure 2: Monitoring damaged interfaces of concrete bridge decks strengthening with FRP measures using guided waves.

There are numerous monitoring techniques developed. Especially for bridge decks, the critical measurands are considered to be mainly deflections and strains, especially for SHM. There are numerous techniques to monitor those measurands both locally (e.g. interface of integrated materials) for the structural members but also globally for the whole bridge. Table 2 summarizes the main techniques for monitoring strains, deflections and strains.

Table 2: Monitoring Techniques for strains and stresses

Measurands	Technique/Method
Displacement/deflections/deformations	Linear variable differential transformer (LVDT)
	3-D laser scanning
	Digital image correlation (DIC)
	Fibre optic-based sensors
Strain	Global positioning (GPS)
	Electrical resistance strain gauges
	Vibrating wire gauge sensors
	Fiber optic-based sensors
	Interferometry
	Digital image correlation (DIC)
Structure changes (e.g. geometry, cracks, voids, delamination, scour)	Electrochemical/electromechanical fatigue sensors
	Visual inspection
	Coin tapping
	3-D laser scanning
	Acoustic emission-based methods
	Automated laser scanning
	Chain dragging
	Hammer sound
	Electrochemical fatigue
	Electrochemical/electromechanical impedance spectroscopy
	Digital image correlation (DIC)
	Ground penetrating radar (GPR)
	Impact echo-based methods
	Infrared thermography
Scour (sonar) devices	
Tilt and slope sensors	
Ultrasonic methods	

For the case of strengthened bridge decks, stresses and strains of the interface can be a hint of disturbance in stress flow due to discontinuities (Achillopoulou&Pau 2017). For example, in the case of a bridge beam strengthened with FRP for enhancing flexural or shear capacity the interface monitoring can indicate damages of various kinds. For example, (Figure 2) damages of the concrete substrate, debondings or delaminations can result in indication of improper stress flow and thus the materials are no longer in contact and loads are no longer transferred.

Guided waves enable many advantages against other techniques. With this technique there is wide range in the kind of wave of the excitation (e.g. Rayleigh, shear waves) and many limitations. It is a technique that can detect by distance and in hidden or non-accessible areas faults, voids, discontinuities, mass disturbance and/or corrosion in one single test. What is more, the nature of the technique, which is based on the reflections and transmissions of the waves, with proper processing can give further

information in order not only to detect, but also characterize and map the damages based on the scattering field (Pau & Achillopoulou 2017, Castaings et al. 2012). The solid media in which the wave travels can change the response and the propagation modes (Pau et al. 2016). The signals can also be amplified, due to the reflections and superpositions of waves. Most of the times decomposition is needed (Spiridonakos & Chatzi 2015). Finally, the frequency and wavelength of the excitation is essential and should be properly specified in order to be able to detect specific ranges of discontinuities.

3 INTERFACE EFFICIENCY INDICES

3.1 Definition of indices

The scattering field of a travelling wave in a solid media is well understood by the reflections and transmissions. A wave interacts with the geometric changes and as such part of it is reflected and returns to the source of the excitation and part of it is transmitted after the discontinuity is encountered.

In the case of a composite cross section, for instance, a reinforced concrete bridge beam strengthened with externally bonded FRP laminate, an extra complexity is faced. The different materials have different densities and mechanical properties. As such the wave propagates with different modes and velocities.

The indices that represent the interface efficiency derive from the scattering field of a monitored interface. Assuming a damaged strengthened beam with a disturbance on the concrete substrate or the FRP itself, the propagating wave will have a reflected amplitude (A_R^d) and a transmitted amplitude (A_T^d). Taken into account the incident wave amplitude of the excitation (A_I^h), the ratio of damaged to healthy response represents the existence of damage. What is more, the ratio of the damaged amplitudes compared to the healthy ones represents the interface capacity to propagate the travelling wave between the two different solid media in partial contact.

As such, the interface efficiency can be expressed by the following equations:

$$I_{int} = \frac{A_I^C - A_I^{FRP}}{A_I^h} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

$$R_{int} = \frac{A_R^C - A_R^{FRP}}{A_R^h} \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$T_{int} = \frac{A_T^C - A_T^{FRP}}{A_T^h} \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Where, I stands for the incident wave (the position of the excitation), R stands for the reflections, T for the transmissions. Superscript C refers to concrete substrate, FRP to the FRP

measure, h refers to the undamaged (healthy) beam, whereas the subscripts int refers to the interface.

3.2 Simulation

This paper studies the example of a simply supported reinforced concrete bridge beam strengthened externally for flexural enhancement with FRP laminate. For these reasons a three-dimensional Finite Element Model (FEM) was developed. The model takes into consideration the cross-section's bottom part where the FRP is integrated. In this work, the simulation includes the substrate of concrete, the interface representing the adhesive layer which helps integrate the FRP to the existing concrete beam and the FRP laminate. The simulations were conducted using ANSYS software. Proper finite elements were chosen for the simulation of concrete, FRP and interface. SOLID185 is used for modeling of 3-D solids, in the case of the study for the concrete substrate and the FRP laminate. The element has eight nodes and three degrees of freedom (translations) at each node. CONTA173 is used to represent contact and sliding between 3-D target surfaces belonging to solids and a deformable surface defined by this element. The element has the same geometric characteristics as the solid face with which it is connected. The materials properties are described in Table 3.

The two scenarios studied in this paper are a) an extensive damage in the concrete substrate and b) a severe discontinuity at the FRP mass at the side of the interface (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Simulated scenarios for FEM (a) damages concrete substrate, (b) damaged FRP laminate

The concrete substrate represented the cover of the concrete beam ($c_{tot}=45mm$) and the width of the beam was 200mm. The FRP laminated thickness was (t_f) 1.3mm whereas the total length of the beam was 4000m.

A sine burst time history of the forcing function was used to select a narrow frequency band and reduce dispersion phenomena and has appropriate spatial

distribution at the support of the beam. The generated excitation was a shear wave with a frequency of 12000 Hz of the forcing function. The wave velocity (c_s) in concrete and the FRP equals to 2300 and 204000 m/sec² respectively. Thus, the regime of the propagating modes is different in the two materials in contact. Structural damping was neglected.

Table 23: Materials' properties

Materials	Modulus of Elasticity E (GPa)	Density ρ (kgr/m ³)	Strength (MPa)
Concrete	33000	2500	Compressive (f_c) 30
Interface	Shear Modulus G 1478 (GPa)	-	Shear (τ) 8.000
FRP	160000	1.6	Tensile (f_t) $219.6 \cdot 10^4$

4 RESULTS

The contour plots of the wave propagation along the solids and the interface are reported. The contour plots show the bottom and upper planes of the concrete substrate and FRP laminate respectively. The interface contour plot is dual, both for the concrete and FRP side.

The indices are calculated according to Equations 1-3 and reported along the length of the interface. The reflections are calculated at a cross section before the damaged cross section, whereas the transmissions at a cross section after the end of the damage.

4.1 Damaged concrete substrate

In the case of a severe damage on the concrete substrate, which is defined by the extension of the damage to the total length of the beam and the depth of the decreased cover. By calculating the ratio of the damages it is derived that there is a 7.5% damaged length and 10% decreased cover of the existing concrete ($L_{dam}/L_{tot}=7.5\%$, $c_{dam}/c_{tot}=10\%$). Given that the current study takes into consideration that the whole width of the beam is damaged, this is considered a severe substrate damage.

The wave propagation of the forcing function is different in concrete and FRP. The wave travels faster in the FRP cross section and encounters earlier the damage. This results in giving earlier reflections.

As the wave propagates, the signal is higher due to the multiple superposition of reflections and transmissions. Its worth noticing that the interface plane behavior differs from concrete side to FRP side. The interface capacity in transferring the excitation forth and backwards is limited due to the damage presence. Also, the different propagating modes affect the reflections and transmissions indices. A further

frequency processing would help better understand the influence of the damage.

t₁

t₂

t₃

t₄

Figure 4: Wave propagation over time (t_1 - t_4) in the case of extensive damage on the concrete substrate $L_{dam}/L_{tot}=7.5\%$, $c_{dam}/c_{tot}=10\%$: contour plots and response (reflections and transmissions)

t_1

t_2

t_3

t_4

4.2 Damaged FRP

The severe damage on the FRP laminate is defined by accounting the extension of the damage to the total length of the beam and the depth of the decreased thickness of the FRP. By calculating the ratio of the damages it is derived that there is a 7.5% damaged length and 77% decreased cover of the existing concrete ($L_{dam}/L_{tot}=7.5\%$, $t_{fdam}/t_{ftot}=77\%$). In this scenario too, the whole width of the beam is damages and as such is considered a severe FRP damage.

The different propagating modes affect the reflections and transmissions indices. In fact, in this scenario, the interface efficiency in propagating the wave is lower. The transmission after the damage is much lower than the ones of the discontinuity located at the concrete substrate. The FRP concentrates the maximums deflections at the edges of the damage cross section and then reflects to the excitation end. The different propagating modes at the substrate and FRP sides is less obvious in this case.

Figure 5: Wave propagation over time (t_1 - t_4) in the case of extensive damage on the concrete substrate $L_{dam}/L_{tot}=7.5\%$, $t_{fdam}/t_{ftot}=77\%$: contour plots and response (reflections and transmissions)

5 CONCLUSIONS

The results of this research help toward understanding the different deflections and response of the interface of a reinforced concrete beam which is strengthened for flexural enhancement with external bonded FRP laminates. The presence of a discontinuity affects the scattering field in both materials and the interface itself.

The results of a non-destructive monitoring technique using guided waves indicate that the interface efficiency in transferring loads and is limited and depends on the depth of the damage and the material in which damage is located. The total deflections of the interface needs tedious interpretation since the different velocities and wave modes should be incorporated in the indices.

This work sets the start for future research of monitoring the interface efficiency in a frequency domain. The investigation of the deflections in this way will give important information for the capacity of the interface to transfer loads and hence assessing the capacity of the asset and furthermore its resilience.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This study has received funding by the European Union H2020- Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research Grants Scheme MSCA-IF-2018 (grant agreement no 845549: BRIFACE- Novel assessment of bridge retrofitting measures through Interface Efficiency Indices (InterFeis) using a Guided Wave-based monitoring method).

REFERENCES

- Achillopoulou, D. V., & Pau, A. (2017). Characterization of defects in plates using shear and Lamb waves. *Procedia engineering*, 199, 2001-2007.
- Achillopoulou, D. V., Kiziridou, A. N., Papachatzakis, G. A., & Karabinis, A. I. (2016). Investigation of interface response of reinforced concrete columns retrofitted with composites. *Steel and Composite Structures*, 22(6), 1337-1358.
- Castaigns, M., Singh, D., & Viot, P. (2012). Sizing of impact damages in composite materials using ultrasonic guided waves. *NDT & E International*, 46, 22-31.
- Dong, Y., Frangopol, D. and Saydam, D. (2013). Time-variant sustainability assessment of seismically vulnerable bridges subjected to multiple hazards. *Earthquake Engineering & Structural Dynamics*, 42(10), pp.1451-1467.
- Frangopol, Dan M. "Life-cycle performance, management, and optimisation of structural systems under uncertainty: accomplishments and challenges 1." *Structure and Infrastructure Engineering* 7.6 (2011): 389-413.
- Iyer, S., Sinha, S. and Schokker, A. (2005). Ultrasonic C-Scan Imaging of Post-Tensioned Concrete Bridge Structures for Detection of Corrosion and Voids. *Computer-Aided Civil and Infrastructure Engineering*, 20(2), pp.79-94.
- Katunin, A., Dragan, K. and Dziendzikowski, M. (2015). Damage identification in aircraft composite structures: A case study using various non-destructive testing techniques. *Composite Structures*, 127, pp.1-9.
- Kundu, T. (2014). Ultrasonic and Electromagnetic Waves for Nondestructive Evaluation and Structural Health Monitoring. *Procedia Engineering*, 86, pp.395-405.
- Pau, A., Achillopoulou, D. V., & Vestroni, F. (2016). Scattering of guided shear waves in plates with discontinuities. *NDT & E International*, 84, 67-75.
- Pau, A., & Achillopoulou, D. (2017). Interaction of Shear and Rayleigh-Lamb Waves with Notches and Voids in Plate Waveguides. *Materials*, 10(7), 841.
- Sayed-Ahmed, E. Y., Bakay, R., & Shrive, N. G. (2009). Bond strength of FRP laminates to concrete: state-of-the-art review. *Electronic Journal of structural engineering*, 9(1), 45-61.
- Spiridonakos, M. D., & Chatzi, E. N. (2015). Meta-modeling of nonstationary uncertain structural systems based on wavelet transform decomposition. *SRESA Journal of Life Cycle Reliability and Safety Engineering*, 4(2), 20-27.